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Abstract—Many data fusion approaches in autonomous driving assume or require data to arrive in an in-sequence order. However, this can generally not be guaranteed for systems with multiple sensors having different transmission and processing latencies. Additionally, latency itself is performance and safety-critical. To ensure safe and efficient driving, latency must be kept minimal. State-of-the-art approaches artificially delay incoming data in an effort to overcome the sequence issue, which drastically increases latency by waiting. Detailed a-priori information about the sensor and transmission characteristics is required, yet, out-of-sequence data cannot be prevented, leading to data loss. In this work, making statistical assumptions reasonable for autonomous driving sensor configurations, we propose an optimal solution providing both guaranteed upper bounds on the data loss and the induced delay. Based on these assumptions, our approach maintains the optimal latency required to ensure in-sequence data ordering. Additionally, by estimating sensor and system characteristics online, our method adaptively adjusts according to the current situation. We demonstrate the superiority of our approach with an extensive evaluation based on both simulated and real-world data. For the latter, using data from an autonomous vehicle emphasizes the importance of our work for intelligent vehicles.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the increasing use of autonomous vehicles and, in general, robotic systems for various tasks, the number of sensors incorporated by these systems is rising [1], [2]. While the required computational power to cope with the data coming from more and more sensors is increasing, the structure of the processing chain undergoes rather minor adjustments [3]. Usually, sensor data is preprocessed before further tasks are applied, such as object detection or semantic segmentation. Then, the results are fused together using different approaches, such as object tracking and grid mapping, before motion and behavior planning are updated with new information.

One key aspect of ensuring proper data fusion is the association of measurements and their acquisition time information. Usually, each sensor contains its own clock and pro-

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Fig. 1. The structure of our approach is illustrated. Given n sensors $S_i \dots S_n$ and m processing modules $P_1 \dots P_m$, data meant for a fusion module is generated, which is generally out-of-sequence. Our approach buffers all processing outputs and forwards data in-sequence to the fusion module. Here, the time difference between the current time and the latest data point forwarded to the fusion module is kept as small as possible while still ensuring in-sequence order.

vides the time of acquisition with its data. Now, if multiple sensors are available and a central fusion approach combines all information, several clocks must be synchronized to avoid data misalignment [4]. To facilitate synchronization in multi-sensor systems in autonomous driving, many sensor manufacturers implemented respective protocols, such as IEEE1588 (PTP) [5], allowing background synchronization without any additional wiring. Additionally, to work properly, fusion algorithms often depend on data arriving in sequence, that is, exactly in the same order as it was acquired. Yet, due to variable transmission and processing latencies, this order is generally mixed up. Especially with recent autonomous systems using multiple processing units [6], transmission latencies are becoming increasingly important. An often-used approach is to artificially delay the fusion stage by the maximum expected latency of any sensor data, which means that all data must be delayed even if data from some sensors is received and processed much faster with lower latencies. However, especially in the domain of autonomous vehicles, low end-to-end latency is crucial for the timely reaction to changes within the highly dynamic environment [7]–[9]. Consequently, with this work, we aim to minimize this additional delay while guaranteeing in-sequence data up to a configurable confidence. By including the fusion processing unit in the sensor synchronization, the data latency can be determined throughout the whole processing stack. The latency, comprising transmission and processing delays, varies at different locations in the processing stack but always increases in the direction of the data flow. Leveraging online estimated data stream characteristics, our

approach minimizes the artificial data delay. With respect to adjustable confidence requirements and based on reasonable assumptions in multi-sensor systems for autonomous driving, our approach provides an optimal solution.

The general structure of our approach is illustrated in Fig. 1. Given a set of sensors and preprocessing modules, we add a special buffer before any module requiring in-sequence data, such as the fusion module. Our approach is evaluated based on simulated data, which allows us to control jitter in latency and update period. We simulate diverse scenarios with different sensors and various update rates to demonstrate the superiority of our approach compared to the current state of the art. Additionally, we show the real-world applicability of our method with a sensor setup that has a total of 12 different sensor streams, consisting of camera, radar, and lidar data.

Summarizing our work in this paper, we present

- a novel adaptive, input latency-based method to guarantee in-sequence data;
- an extensive evaluation based on simulated and real-world data using various sensor configurations;
- an open-source C++ and Python library¹

II. RELATED WORK

The issue of latency in robotic and autonomous systems has been investigated before. Its impact on fusion systems is presented [10]–[12]. The authors of [11] proposed an exact solution to the out-of-sequence problem if the fusion allows retrodiction. However, respective approaches are not always available. An overview of different, universal strategies to deal with heterogeneous update rates and processing times is given in [4]. Here, the authors investigate the behavior with respect to a central fusion system, similar to the structure illustrated in Fig. 1. The authors of [4] show that, in some cases, data must be forwarded to a fusion system in-sequence since the filtering approach often only allows going forward in time.

A more recent survey [2] summarizes the handling of heterogeneous sensor data fusion with regard to the handling of out-of-sequence data reception into two major approaches: buffering and reprocessing. Buffering induces a delay with which the fusion modules run in the past to allow data with a higher latency to be included in the fusion process. The delay thereby depends on the largest possible latency of all sensor processing paths. In contrast, reprocessing is generally able to include incoming data without any further delay. This, however, involves an immense computational effort. Similar to before, incoming data is buffered first. Then, all buffered data is processed in a copy of the fusion module. If data arrives out-of-sequence, the fusion module is copied from a persistent state, and all buffered data is processed again. At a threshold in time, it is assumed that no more out-of-sequence data arrives within a certain interval, and the persistent state is updated using all buffered data within the interval. The computational expenses of reprocessing

Fig. 2. Here, the approach of measuring latency is illustrated. At first, a sensor S_i tags its data with the time of acquisition (red arrow). During processing, this timestamp is kept, meaning that all data resulting from the sensor data is tagged with the same timestamp. This allows a precise measure of the data latency at any point in the software stack, which is exemplarily represented by dashed lines.

strongly depend on an accepted delay and the required update rate. With a rising number of sensors and, consecutively, input data, reprocessing can become infeasible due to its processing cost.

The authors of [13] propose an approach that combines reprocessing and retrodiction to a specific tracking system. Here, tracks are updated with out-of-sequence measurements, and their influence is later decorrelated to allow in-sequence-like processing. While this is beneficial for some tracking systems, the approach is highly specific and not generally available for other fusion processing modules.

In contrast to the presented approaches, our proposed method aims to improve the buffering approach by adaptively setting the required delay while ensuring in-sequence processing. For this, update rates and latencies of incoming data are tracked, and an in-sequence data order is estimated. By matching incoming data to the estimated order, it can be decided if data needs to be buffered or forwarded immediately. To the best of our knowledge, we are the first to propose such an approach.

III. FOUNDATIONS

In this section, we present existing methods and fundamentals required for our contribution presented later

A. Latency Estimation

A key aspect of our approach is the consideration of the latency data arrives with. For this, it must be measured first. Generally, latency cannot be measured directly from data alone. This means that without further information, the latency of, e.g., a lidar scan or camera image, cannot be deduced from the raw data. As a consequence, we require sensors to tag their output data with the time stamp at which the data was acquired. This allows data latency to be determined at any point in the software stack by comparing the tagged timestamp with the current time. Fig. 2 illustrates this approach for two processing streams emerging from the same sensor. Admittedly, all sensors need to be synchronized and be able to tag their data respectively. Generally, this might entail a certain effort to synchronize sensors, but in recent years, most manufacturers of sensors used in autonomous vehicles implemented the precision time protocol

¹https://github.com/uulm-mrm/minimal_latency_in_sequence_buffer

Fig. 3. The connection between the original update period and the update period at reception is illustrated. Assuming that the latency $l \in \mathbb{R}$ and update period $r \in \mathbb{R}$ are Gaussian distributed, the update period at reception time $\bar{r} \in \mathbb{R}$ is subject to a higher variance as the original one.

(PTP) [5], which allows synchronizing sensors precisely in the background.

With each received data sample, the data latency can now be measured. Since data is subject to noise and may vary over time, our approach later uses the exponentially weighted moving mean and variance (EWMA/V) to estimate the latency characteristics for every data stream. A detailed description of an unbiased estimation of these values is given later in Section III-C.

B. Update Period Estimation

Similar to the latency, the update period of streams is also used in our approach later. Thus, it must be estimated and tracked.

To estimate the update period of a stream, a naive approach would consider the times of reception. However, as illustrated in Fig. 3, the update period variance at reception differs from the original one of the stream since it depends on the latency. Respectively, to reliably estimate the update period, only the original timestamp may be used.

Since the update period, analogous to the latency, is subject to noise and may vary over time, we similarly use the EWMA/V to estimate the characteristics of every stream.

C. Exponentially Weighted Running Mean and Variance

In this section, the unbiased EWMA/V estimator is presented. We use it to track the two previously presented data stream characteristics, i.e., the update rate and latency, which are subject to noise and may vary over time. For efficient processing, an iterative algorithm is additionally provided.

An algorithm to calculate the unbiased mean and variance of a set of samples is provided in [14], and an iterative method is presented in [15]. Introducing weights, the author of [16] presents a weighted iterative algorithm. For better readability, here, the closed form is presented first. Given a set of samples $x_i \in \mathbb{R}$ and respective weights $w_i \in \mathbb{R}$ the estimated mean $\hat{\mu} \in \mathbb{R}$ and variance $\hat{\sigma}^2 \in \mathbb{R}$ are defined by

$$\hat{\mu} = \frac{1}{V_1} \sum_i w_i x_i \quad (1)$$

$$\hat{\sigma}^2 = \frac{V_1}{V_1^2 - V_2} \sum_i w_i (x_i - \hat{\mu})^2, \quad (2)$$

with $V_1 = \sum_i w_i$ and $V_2 = \sum_i w_i^2$. To evaluate Eq. (1)&(2), all samples and weights must be known, and the sum must be

explicitly evaluated. Hence, an iterative algorithm provides an improved performance for large sample sets. Starting with $m_0 = 0$, $s_0 = 0$, $p_0 = 0$, and $q_0 = 0$ the iterative update is given by [17]

$$p_{k+1} = p_k + w_{k+1} \quad (3)$$

$$q_{k+1} = q_k + w_{k+1}^2 \quad (4)$$

$$m_{k+1} = m_k + \frac{w_{k+1}}{p_{k+1}} (x_{k+1} - m_k) \quad (5)$$

$$s_{k+1} = s_k + w_{k+1} \cdot (x_{k+1} - m_k) \cdot (x_{k+1} - m_{k+1}). \quad (6)$$

Then, the mean $\hat{\mu}_k$ and variance $\hat{\sigma}_k^2$ at step k are defined by

$$\hat{\mu}_k = m_k \quad (7)$$

$$\hat{\sigma}_k^2 = \frac{p_k}{p_k^2 - q_k} s_k. \quad (8)$$

Here, p_k is the sum of weights, and q_k is the sum of quadratic weights.

To yield exponential decay, the weights w_i can be set respectively. Since weights depend on their index difference from the most recent sample index, they change over time. While the closed-form estimation can be applied without further changes, the iterative approach is not yet able to deal with changing weights. Given the decay factor $\alpha \in [0, 1] \subset \mathbb{R}$ the adapted iterative update is defined by [17]

$$p_{k+1} = \alpha p_k + 1 \quad (9)$$

$$q_{k+1} = \alpha^2 q_k + 1^2 \quad (10)$$

$$m_{k+1} = \alpha m_k + x_{k+1} \quad (11)$$

$$s_{k+1} = \alpha s_k + (x_{k+1} - \frac{m_k}{p_k}) \cdot (x_{k+1} - \frac{m_{k+1}}{p_{k+1}}), \quad (12)$$

where the mean $\hat{\mu}_k$ and variance $\hat{\sigma}_k^2$ at step k are given by

$$\hat{\mu}_k = \frac{1}{p_k} m_k \quad (13)$$

$$\hat{\sigma}_k^2 = \frac{p_k}{p_k^2 - q_k} s_k. \quad (14)$$

Now, $\hat{\mu}_k$ of Eq. (13) and $\hat{\sigma}_k^2$ of Eq. (14) represent the EWMA/V at step k , respectively.

With the presented iterative algorithm, the previously introduced entities, i.e., latency and update period, can be efficiently estimated, which is of interest for the proposed method in Section IV.

IV. METHOD

In this section, the structure and functionality of our approach is derived. As shown in Fig. 1, the goal of this work is to provide a buffer-like module that can be plugged into existing software structures. Given an arbitrary number of input streams with different update rates and latencies, this buffer converts an arbitrary input sequence with possible out-of-sequence measurements into an in-sequence output while keeping the additional delay as minimal as possible.

Fig. 4. Here, the estimated sequence is illustrated based on given inputs of two sensors (green and blue). The dotted line marks the current time. Acquisition and reception times are marked with downward and upward-facing arrows, respectively. Dashed arrows represent the estimated sequence. Gray arrows mark received data which is held back since previously acquired data is expected but not yet received (black dashed arrow). Exemplary confidence intervals for \hat{t}_2 , \hat{t}_3 , and \hat{t}_4 are depicted as colored areas on the time axis.

A. Sequence Estimation

As a first step, the update rate and latency of all input streams are estimated using the approaches presented in Section III. For each data stream d_k the results are an estimated mean update rate $\hat{\mu}_{r,k}$ and latency $\hat{\mu}_{l,k}$ and respective variances $\hat{\sigma}_{r,k}^2$ and $\hat{\sigma}_{l,k}^2$. Based on this, every time a data sample is received, possible future data samples are generated. With the data sample $d_{k,i}$ from stream k received at the time t_i with acquisition time stamp t'_i the reception time \hat{t}_{i+j} of the j -th next estimated data sample $\hat{d}_{k,i+j}$ is described by

$$\hat{t}_{i+j} \sim \mathcal{N}(t'_i + j\hat{\mu}_{r,k} + \hat{\mu}_{l,k}, j\hat{\sigma}_{r,k}^2 + \hat{\sigma}_{l,k}^2). \quad (15)$$

For this distribution, given a confidence value a , a confidence interval $I_{i+j}^a = [\underline{t}_{i+j}, \bar{t}_{i+j}]$ can be calculated, such that

$$P(t_{i+j} \in I_{i+j}^a) = a, \quad (16)$$

which, for Gaussian distributions, is related to the inverse error function. In this work, the confidence interval is always set symmetrically with respect to the mean value. For readability reasons, the numbering of streams is often replaced by different colors. For example, the two streams $d_{1,i}$ and $d_{2,j}$ are represented by d_i and d_j .

B. Sequence Matching

Given the entities described in the previous section, a sequence of incoming data is estimated. Here, each data stream is considered separately using its estimated mean and variance. Whenever data is received, it is matched against the estimated data sequence. Since the data stream is given, it only needs to be matched against a single sequence. If no data from other streams is expected to be acquired previously, the received data is forwarded directly. Otherwise, if data is expected to be acquired earlier but has not been received yet, the incoming data is held back. In this case, it is only held back up until the upper bound of the confidence interval of the earlier acquired data. If the earlier acquired data arrives

Fig. 5. The acquisition order decision process based on the confidence interval of measurement times is illustrated here. Only estimations are available until data is received (a). The mean would indicate that the green stream is acquiring first. When some of the data is received, the acquisition time is updated, and the estimated acquisition order may change at the same time (b). Here, the blue stream may be acquired before the green one.

within the interval, both are forwarded together; otherwise, it is assumed to be lost, and the received data is forwarded.

The described process is illustrated in Fig. 4. For this, acquisition and reception sequences, as well as latencies and confidence intervals, are depicted. More detailed, at the current time d_3 has already been received at t_3 , but d_2 is expected to be acquired before d_3 , thus, to ensure in-sequence processing, d_3 is held back. d_2 is expected within a confidence interval. As soon as it is received, it is forwarded directly together with d_3 . If, however, no measurement is received until the end of the confidence interval, d_3 is forwarded, and d_2 is assumed to be lost.

C. Decision Making

In Fig. 4, the measurement time $t'_{k,i}$ is depicted as an arrow at a specific time point for illustration reasons. However, the estimated update period distribution must be considered instead to decide on the possible order of measurements. More specifically, the approach described in Section III-B yields a Gaussian distribution for the estimated measurement sequence. Given an estimated data sample $\hat{d}_{k,i}$ of a stream and a confidence value b , which generally differs from a in Eq. (16), the measurement time confidence interval $I_i^{b'} = [\underline{t}'_i, \bar{t}'_i]$ can be calculated. For multiple streams, the estimated acquisition sequence is generated based on the lower bound of all estimated data points. Whenever data is received, the lower bound is replaced by the actual acquisition time. While this seems trivial at first, it shall be mentioned that replacing the estimated time with the actual time may change the estimated acquisition sequence. As a consequence, similar to the situation in Fig. 5, data must be held back due to possible out-of-order acquisition. In Fig. 5, e.g., d_i is affected by this. It is held back, although the mean update period of d_i suggests that d_i was acquired afterward. To determine the acquisition sequence online, the confident buffer time is used, which is defined in the next section.

D. Times and Delays

Using the approach described in the previous sections, data is delayed implicitly. In this section, specific times are defined to characterize the current buffer state, i.e., up to which time the buffer has forwarded all data and when the next sample is expected. Further, respective types of delays

are investigated in more detail. For this, the times and delays are defined first, then an example is given for the presented sequence in Fig. 4.

First, no data will be forwarded by a buffer with an acquisition time earlier than the guaranteed processing time (GPT). It is defined as

Definition 1 (Guaranteed Processed Time). Given a set of n streams $S = \{d_1, \dots, d_n\}$ with respective data samples $d_i = \{t_{k,i}, t'_{k,i}\}$ that have been received by a buffer, the guaranteed processing time t_{GPT} is the acquisition time $t'_{k,i}$ of the last forwarded data sample.

Next, based on a required confidence value b , the confident processing time (CPT) is an estimated time. With a probability of $p = (1 - b)/2$ no data will arrive with an earlier acquisition time stamp than the CPT for each stream.

Definition 2 (Confident Processed Time). Let b be a confidence value and $S = \{d_1, \dots, d_n\}$ be a set of n streams. Further, let $\hat{D} = \{\hat{d}_{k,i+j}\}$ be a set of all estimated data samples, with $\hat{d}_{k,i}$ being the last received data sample of the respective stream. Given the estimated acquisition time confidence intervals $I_{i+j}^b = [t'_{k,i+j}, \bar{t}'_{k,i+j}]$ for each estimated data sample $\hat{d}_{k,i+j} \in \hat{D}$, the confident processed time t_{CPT}^b with respect to the confidence value b is defined as the earliest lower bound of all confidence intervals, such that

$$t_{CPT}^b = \min_{\hat{D}} t'_{k,i+j}. \quad (17)$$

Besides the time definition above, two types of delays are introduced next. First, the induced delay denotes the maximum delay any received data point is held back. It determines how much delay is induced by the buffer in contrast to the direct processing of incoming data.

Definition 3 (Induced delay). Let $S = \{d_1, \dots, d_n\}$ be a set of n streams. Further, let $D = \{d_{k,i} = \{t_{k,i}, t'_{k,i}\}\}$ be a set of received data samples that have been received but not forwarded. Given the time t , the induced delay Δt is defined as

$$\Delta t = t - \min_D t_{k,i}. \quad (18)$$

Consecutively, the induced delay of a specific sample $d_{k,i}$ is defined as the buffer's induced delay at the time the sample is forwarded.

Last, based on a confidence value b , the confidence-induced delay (CID) reflects the delay with which a subsequent fusion module must be kept in the past to still allow in-sequence processing.

Definition 4 (Confident Induced delay). With b , t_{CPT}^b from Definition 2, and the time t the CID $\Delta t'$ is defined by

$$\Delta t' = t - t_{CPT}^b \quad (19)$$

Based on the scenario in Fig. 4, an example of the delays defined above is given in Fig. 6. It can be seen that the CID value is always less than the maximal latency of a sensor

Fig. 6. Exemplary delay progression for the scenario of Fig. 4 is plotted. For this, an update rate variance $\mu_r = 0.1$ and a confidence value $b = 0.95$ was chosen.

(1.5s) plus half the confidence interval (0.15s). Further, the induced delay is only greater than zero if data is held back, and it increases until data is forwarded. Generally, both entities may jump to any lower value but must not jump upward.

V. EXPERIMENTS

In this Section, we present the results of our evaluation based on simulated and real-world data. All experiments were run on a computer containing an AMD Ryzen™ 9 7950X CPU, and 64GB of DDR5 RAM. If not differently stated, simulated experiments have been conducted using Monte Carlo simulation with 1000 runs.

A. Simulation

Using simulation, we first present the general functionality of our approach in near-perfect conditions, i.e., the mean and variance of the update period and latency are constant, and no data is dropped. Then, jumps in the update period and latency are added, and some sensor data is dropped.

In the first experiment, two streams, $d_1 = d$ and $d_2 = d$, are simulated. The update periods and latencies are given by

$$\mu_r = 100 \text{ ms}, \sigma_r = 1 \text{ ms}, \mu_l = 100 \text{ ms}, \sigma_l = 10 \text{ ms}, \quad (20)$$

$$\mu_r = 50 \text{ ms}, \sigma_r = 1 \text{ ms}, \mu_l = 15 \text{ ms}, \sigma_l = 1 \text{ ms}. \quad (21)$$

Over a period of 30s, data for both streams is simulated and pushed into our proposed buffer. The confidence values are set to $a = 0.99$ and $b = 0.99$. The decay factor for the EWMA/V estimator is set to $\alpha = 0.95$. Whenever data is forwarded, the induced delay is measured. Further, the rate at which data is dropped due to violated assumptions is determined. Our proposed approach (OURS) is compared to a fixed lag buffer with two different delays of 100ms and 123.38ms, respectively, which are referred to as FIXED1 and FIXED2. Thereby, the delay of FIXED2 was chosen as the 99% quantile of the delay of high latency stream (cf. Eq. (15)), given that all stream parameters are known. The induced delay results are illustrated in Fig. 7. Since d has a higher latency and a lower update rate, it can almost always be forwarded directly and, thus, is never held back by OURS. Further, OURS drops 0.80% of d_i and 0.0% of d_i , which fits the chosen confidence values that represent upper bounds. In contrast, FIXED1 drops 48.56% of d_i and 0.0% of d_i , and FIXED2 drops 0.80% of d_i and 0.0% of d_i . Since no stream

Fig. 7. Here, the induced delays for the first experiment with the two streams, d and \hat{d} are displayed. The results using our approach (OURS) are compared to the results using different fixed leg buffers (FIXED1 & FIXED2). The median is marked in green, the box denotes the 25% to 75% quantile, and the whiskers represent the max/min values.

sequence information is available with fixed lag buffers, data must often be held back unnecessarily. Considering the drop rates together with the induced delay in Fig. 7, OURS provides the lowest rate of dropped messages while, at the same time, achieving the lowest median induced delay. Our approach generally adapts to any period and latency, i.e., no parameter of Eq. (20) & Eq. (21) is known to the buffer. This allows it to fit into any given scenario; however, using fixed leg buffers requires knowing all parameters beforehand, and each parameter is fixed, leading to suboptimal results.

The second simulated scenario contains the same two streams d and \hat{d} . In the beginning, their parameters are the same as in the first experiment, with the difference that 5% of samples are dropped and not forwarded to the buffer. Then, after 15 s, the parameters of the stream d are changed to

$$\mu_r = 50 \text{ ms}, \sigma_r = 1 \text{ ms}, \mu_l = 25 \text{ ms}, \sigma_l = 5 \text{ ms}, \quad (22)$$

which means more data is available with less latency. Again, our approach is compared to FIXED1 and FIXED2. Results are presented in Fig. 8. Drop rates are similar to the first experiment, with the exception that after the change with OURS, the drop rate of d increases to the same level as for \hat{d} which still adheres to the demanded confidence and with FIXED1 and FIXED2 there are practically no drops. Due to the online estimation of update period and latency, OURS is able to adapt to the new situation after the parameter change, and thus, the induced delay can be substantially reduced. However, with FIXED1 and FIXED2, parameters may not be changed adaptively, yielding worse results for d and similar results for \hat{d} . To present the parameter estimation of OURS in more detail, Fig. 9 shows the progression of the update period and latency estimation. The parameter change at 15 s can easily be made out, and the estimated variance is increased immediately. After some time, the new parameters are accurately estimated, which allows the buffer to adapt to these changes. As a result, the induced delay is significantly decreased.

B. Real-World

In this section, we present the results of our third experiment based on real-world data. For this, we used data from an autonomous vehicle equipped with 8 cameras, 2 lidar,

Fig. 8. The induced delay results of the second experiment are illustrated here. For each stream, the left box denotes the induced delay prior to, and the right box after the parameter change of stream d .

Fig. 9. Here, the estimation results for the update period and latency of d are illustrated. The median value is marked by the blue line, and the 25% to 75% area is illustrated in gray.

and 5 radar sensors [18]. Due to some issues related to the data recording of some sequences, we excluded the two rear-facing radar sensors from our evaluation. Lidar sensors are triggered at 10 Hz, cameras at 10 Hz, and radar sensors at 12.5 Hz. Using PTP [5], the acquisition time is known for cameras and lidar sensors. Acquisition times of radar data are estimated based on the raw data reception time.

Object detection is applied to each sensor's data, leading to one stream per sensor. The output of the object detection is fed to the buffer under test. Since no ground truth period and latency information is available, the delay of FIXED1 and FIXED2 have been set such that FIXED1 yields similar induced delays to OURS and FIXED2 yields a similar drop rate to OURS. In this case, the delays were 180 ms and 225 ms for FIXED1 and FIXED2, respectively. The results of an approx. 30 s excerpt are presented in Fig. 10. Given the settings above, OURS and FIXED2 yield a drop rate of approx. 3%, and FIXED1 of approx. 48%. For better readability, all streams originating from the same sensor type are combined.

Using FIXED1 is practically infeasible since almost half of the data is dropped. Comparing OURS to FIXED2 shows that, while yielding the same drop rate, our approach can significantly improve the induced delay, here by a factor of two.

Summarizing our evaluation based on experiments using both simulated and real-world data, OURS has proven superior to other state-of-the-art approaches. The comparisons show that either the latency or drop rate is substantially reduced, allowing for less delayed or more precise subsequent

Fig. 10. The results of the real-world experiment are presented here. Streams originating from cameras are denoted by d , from lidars by d , and from radars by d .

data fusion. OURS can be deployed without any requirement on other modules, enabling broad applicability.

VI. CONCLUSION

To summarize this work, we proposed a novel approach to ensure the in-sequence processing of data coming from multiple streams with different and changing characteristics. Our approach provides guarantees about the induced delay and data drop rates based on user-defined confidence requirements. Compared to other state-of-the-art approaches, our method always yields the smallest delays while preserving a low data drop rate. It is generally applicable and thus increases the performance of any system that requires in-sequence input data. For future work, combining our approach with a post-hoc reprocessing approach seems intriguing, as our approach should reduce the required computation expense.

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